

INTEGRATION OF MODERN WEB TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

The article talks about the integration of modern web technologies into the higher education educational processes. The relevance of the topic lies in the use of innovative educational technologies in the educational process.

The Internet is a global telecommunication network of information and computing resources that connects users of various organizations, government agencies, and private users. The growth rate of the Internet is 15% per month. The integration of information technologies into the educational process is a necessary condition for the modernization of the higher professional education system. In recent years, the rapid development of web technologies has been observed, which created the need to develop and introduce new methods of using the Internet into the educational process, the purpose of which is not only to increase the effectiveness of learning, but also to form professional, informational and intellectual competencies of students. is to create conditions.

The following forms of using web technologies in education are known. The first is mixed education, which includes the integration of digital and innovative educational technologies into the traditional educational process in order to improve the quality of teaching university subjects and encourage the development of students' information competences.

The second form is distance education, which involves organizing the educational process without the direct participation of the teacher, encouraging students' independent cognitive activities, self-organization and self-learning. based on web technologies that allow to develop self-education skills. The third form is represented by new educational concepts - the concept of open educational resources and mass open online courses aimed at creating an individual educational path that combines formal and informal educational forms and methods.

Open educational resources increase the openness of education, ensure its continuity, simplify the use of electronic educational content and increase its quality.

However, it should be noted that since most web resources are not adapted to the educational system, working with them requires special training. In addition, the information posted on many web resources is characterized by a high level of uncertainty and redundancy. A significant part of the information on the Internet is constantly repeated and duplicated, which inevitably leads to an increase in its total volume. It should be noted that against the background of the huge increase in the amount of information, it is becoming more and more difficult for the user to find what is necessary and useful. All this requires a certain level of digital literacy, information competence, a culture of intellectual activity and adequate, focused behavior of students.

One of the manifestations of the reaction to the above problems is the emergence of cognitive, information and communication barriers in some students, and even emotional rejection of the Internet. In some cases, students themselves are not able to search and further process information posted on the Internet. In addition, students often suffer from negative information. An ever-expanding network of commercial organizations providing various educational services brings additional challenges.

The integration of pedagogical and information technologies can be done in different ways. The most important ways are highlighted: interaction of individual elements of pedagogical and web technologies; introduction of elements of information technology into educational technologies and vice versa; qualitatively changing the interacting elements of various technologies; enrichment of the main educational technologies used with elements of information technologies; are new digital tools that allow for the modernization of pedagogical technologies, the effective use of public open online courses and open educational resources. In order to define the concept of "web technology", it is necessary to reveal the essence of the concept of "educational technology" in accordance with the original meaning of the concept of "technology", because the first comes from the second.

The content of the original "technology" concept includes:

- first, the process of processing and transformation, as a result of which the finished product;
- secondly, the normative side of this process, which determines how and what needs to be done in order for the necessary transformation processes to occur.

Technology comes from the Greek words *techne* (art, skill, science) and *logos* (concept, teaching, knowledge). It can be assumed that technology in a broad sense should be understood as scientific knowledge of skills, arts and crafts. In the explanatory dictionary, the concept of technology is a set of techniques used in any business, skill or art.

First of all, social services of the World Wide Web are used, which provide organization of secure search of information, posting of information on blogs, joint editing of documents, posting of photos, presentations, implementation of Wiki (Wikipedia), etc.

Secondly, use services based on the Internet protocol system (TCP/IP protocol stack): mail (SMTP, POP3, IMAP4), hypertext (HTTP), telecommunications (Skype) and file transfer (FTP).

Thirdly, use different types of special programs: instant messaging programs (Miranda IM, Jimm, ICQ, QIP, Mail.ru Agent, MSN Messenger, Yahoo, Messenger), organizing communication between site visitors (forum, chat) .

Internet resources are a collection of information technologies and databases accessible through these technologies and available in a constant update mode.

The most important concept for us is "web technology". Web technologies - an automated environment for receiving, processing, storing, transmitting and using knowledge in the form of information and its implementation on the Internet, we can distinguish the following:

- * Computer training programs (electronic textbooks, simulators, laboratory exercises, test systems);
- * Educational systems based on multimedia technologies built using personal computers, video equipment, optical discs;
- * Intellectual and educational expert systems used in various fields of science;
- * Databases distributed across networks;
- * Telecommunication facilities, including e-mail, newsgroups, local and regional communication networks, data networks, etc.;
- * Electronic libraries, distributed and centralized publishing systems.

Technologies can be divided
into two large groups:

Selective
interactivity

Full
interactivity

The first type includes all technologies that ensure the storage of information in a structured form - data banks, databases. These technologies are selectively interactive and data is provided as a service. The user is not allowed to enter new data.

The second type includes technologies that provide direct access to large volumes of data stored in databases and data banks. This type of technology includes all forms of computer-mediated communication: e-mail, teleconferencing, synchronous and asynchronous communication, etc. Education is carried out on the computer network of Internet resources:

- * Information products of the work of experts dealing with educational issues;
- * Computer training programs, including electronic textbooks, simulators, laboratory workshops, test systems;
- * Educational systems based on multimedia technologies built on the basis of personal use computers, video equipment, optical discs;
- * Distributed databases across networks.

Online learning resources include:

- * Personal web pages reflecting the author's teaching experience;
- * Websites and presentations that reflect various aspects of teaching activities.

Today, the number of educational institutions connecting to the Internet within the framework of various state programs for the development of education is increasing. On the one hand, educational institutions meet the need to join the open information space using the Internet, and on the other hand, they begin to look for opportunities to implement educational goals and objectives. The main task of a modern school is to develop the student's personality, to change and change his qualities, to create conditions for the student to become a full-fledged citizen of the world information community.

The active use of web technologies and telecommunications in the full-time educational process allows us to talk about the implementation of innovative processes, through which other types of changes take place: the goals and content of educational programs, forms and methods of teaching will change. With the help of web technologies, teachers and students can use Internet services to facilitate learning and speed up the learning process.

The choice of reasonable and optimal solutions when integrating information-pedagogical technologies and systematic positions is based, first of all, on the analysis of education based on the new integrated technology or its effectiveness, that is, on the evaluation of the effectiveness of the interaction between the teacher and students. A distinctive feature of this interaction is the creative activity of the teacher and students both in the learning process and in the learning process, which in many ways affects not only the teacher's professional skills and the knowledge of students, but also it depends on the emotional mood created during the educational process, the educational process, as well as the availability of appropriate incentives, educational conditions and many other factors.

The rapid development of information and communication technologies and the widespread use of the Internet led to a qualitative change in educational technologies used throughout the world. Blended learning is becoming the most popular form of education today, where computer-based learning tools are widely used in the educational process.

Internet technologies in education make the educational process more interesting, provide the necessary information at the right time, participate in scientific projects, and are used to connect students with each other and with teachers. The introduction of Internet technologies into the educational process is determined by the knowledge obtained earlier and the results obtained today, which forms the educational process. Powerful software and its full integration with the Internet give students the opportunity to share information gained in the process of mastering new knowledge. The introduction of modern web technologies into education is due to the fact that the student receives a large amount of knowledge necessary for work in the process of communicating with people who are experts in certain issues - the so-called informal education.

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